

Pitch: Course/Training for 'FAIRification through the Research Data Life Cycle'

Providing hands-on training and support for making research data FAIR through all stages of research

v 6.0 Final (September 9, 2022)

Output from 'FAIRification as a Service' Taskforce (Q2-2022 – Q3-2022)
Leiden University (LEI) / Leiden University Medical Center (LUMC)

Intended audience: Data Management Network, Digital Competance Centers (DCCs), faculty boards, data stewards

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Background

- FAIR* (meta)data is key for the success of open science and research reproducibility, two drivers of LEI and LUMC research agendas
- FAIR (meta)data is increasingly required by funders
- FAIR (meta)data is a part of the data management policy at LEI and LUMC
- FAIR (meta)data implementation is guided by different approaches/methods and tools at various stages of development

Problem

- Lack of general understanding among researchers about metadata, which serve as the foundation for initiating FAIRification
- No Leiden framework for delivering and supporting the use of such FAIR implementation (or 'FAIRification') approaches/methods and tools to researchers of LEI and LUMC
- No comprehensive resource at Leiden to guide LEI and LUMC researchers in the choices of FAIRification with respect to either the approach/method/tool complexity and maturity or the stage of research data life cycle

*see slide 12 for the FAIR Guiding Principles

Goal

We want to embed the FAIRification of (meta)data into the research lifecycle at LEI and LUMC to better support (1) researchers (2) funder requirements and (3) LEI and LUMC RDM policies

Solution

- Develop a course or workshop series that provides and teaches researchers FAIRification methods and tools over the research data lifecycle

Learning objectives

- Define research metadata and its different types
- Share available FAIRification approaches/methods and tools, addressing complexity and maturity
- Map FAIRification and metadata across the research data lifecycle
- Teach most mature tools for FAIRifying (meta)data and how they connect to the LEI and LUMC RDM environments

Aim

We want to provide LEI and LUMC researchers the resources, tools, and support to FAIRify their data throughout the research data lifecycle

**FAIRification
methods differ
in approach**

- Bring Your Own Data (BYOD) workshops
- Three-point FAIRification Framework (3PFF) via Metadata for Machines (M4M) workshops and FAIR Implementation Profile (FIP) workshops

**FAIRification
tools differ
in maturity & complexity**

- CEDAR templates
- FIP Wizard
- Ontop
- RightField
- FAIR Data Point Metadata Editor
- Open Refine
- Nanobench
- YODA

**FAIRification
needs differ
through the lifecycle**

- Collecting data – R1.2; I1; F2, I2, R1.3
- Processing & Analyzing data – R1.2; I1; F2, I2, R1.3
- Publishing & Sharing data – A1.1; A1.2; R1.1
- Preserving data – F1, F3, F4, A1, A2, I3, R1
- Re-using data – F1

Potential course schedule (4 half days; 1 full day) – overview

MONDAY

Session 1
(half day)

Online or in-person or hybrid

Introduction to metadata

2 hours

- What is metadata?
- And its types?
- Why is it useful?
- How is metadata mapped over the data lifecycle?

Introduction to FAIR

2 hours

- What is FAIR? (*Findable, accessible, interoperable, reusable; Fully AI Ready*)
- What are FAIR data and services?
- Why is it useful?
- How is FAIR mapped over the data lifecycle?

TUESDAY

Session 2
(half day)

Ideally in-person

Methods and Tools

2 hours

- What are FAIRification approaches/methods and tools?
- How are they mapped over the data lifecycle?
- Address complexity and maturity
- Address integration with LU and LUMC

VI. Re-using – F1

2 hours

- Introduce data set that will serve as hands-on example
- Share tool(s) that address principles at this stage in lifecycle

**starting with re-using as it addresses F1 and student's will be 're-using' the example dataset for the course*

WEDNESDAY

Session 3
(half day)

Ideally in-person

II. Collecting – R1.2; I1; F2, I2, R1.3

and

III. Processing & Analyzing – R1.2; I1; F2, I2, R1.3

4 hours

- Share tool(s) that address principles at this stage in lifecycle
- Use the example data set for hand-on training of tools

**these two steps in the cycle share principles*

THURSDAY

Session 4
(half day)

Ideally in-person

IV. Publishing & Sharing – A1.1; A1.2; R1.1

and

V. Preserving – F1, F3, F4, A1, A2, I3, R1

4 hours

- Share tool(s) that address principles at this stage in lifecycle
- Use the example data set for hand-on training of tools

**these two steps in the cycle add to those addressed in early days or share the A principles*

FRIDAY

Session 5
(full day)

Must be in-person

'Hackathon' – Bring your own data

3 hours

- Help guide through the cycle with the tools for the previous days but on data brought by the students

I. Planning with a FAIRification Plan

2 hours

- Develop a 'FAIRification Roadmap' with the students for their data (connect with DMPs)

Closing session

1 hours (+1 hour optional)

- Final questions and discussion
- Summarize learnings

MONDAY Session 1 (half day)

13:00 – 13:10 Round of introductions

13:10 – 14:00 Intro. to metadata

- What is metadata?
- And its types?
- Why is it useful?

14:00 – 14:10 Break

14:10 – 15:00 Intro. to metadata cont.

- Why is it useful?
- How is metadata mapped over the data lifecycle?

15:00 – 15:10 Break

15:10 – 16:00 Intro. to FAIR

- What is FAIR? (*Findable, accessible, interoperable, reusable; Fully AI Ready*)
- What are FAIR data and services?

16:00 – 16:10 Break

16:10 – 17:00 Intro. to FAIR cont.

- Why is it useful?
- How is FAIR mapped over the data lifecycle?

TUESDAY Session 2 (half day)

13:00 – 13:10 Intro. to rest of the course

13:10 – 14:00 Methods & Tools

- What are FAIRification approaches/methods and tools?
- How are they mapped over the data lifecycle?

14:00 – 14:10 Break

14:10 – 15:00 Methods & Tools

- Address complexity and maturity
- Address integration with LEI and LUMC

15:00 – 15:10 Break

Re-using – F1

15:10 – 16:00 Intro. to tool & example data

- Introduce data set that will serve as hands-on example
- Share tool(s) that address principles at this stage in lifecycle

16:00 – 16:10 Break

16:10 – 17:00 Working session

- Working session using the example data

Potential course schedule – details

WEDNESDAY (THURSDAY)

Session 3 (Session 4)
(half days)

Collecting – R1.2; I1; F2, I2, R1.3 (Publishing & Sharing – A1.1; A1.2; R1.1)

13:00 – 13:50 Intro. to tool & example data

13:50 – 14:00 Break

14:00 – 14:50 Working session

14:50 – 15:00 Break

Processing & Analyzing – R1.2; I1; F2, I2, R1.3 (Preserving – F1, F3, F4, A1, A2, I3, R1)

15:00 – 15:50 Intro. to tool & example data

15:50 – 16:00 Break

16:00 – 16:50 Working session

16:50 – 17:00 Recap & questions

- Share tool(s) that address principles at this stage in lifecycle
- Use the example data set for hand-on training of tools

- Working session using the example data

- Share tool(s) that address principles at this stage in lifecycle
- Use the example data set for hand-on training of tools

- Working session using the example data

FRIDAY

Session 5
(full day)

9:00 – 9:30 Intro. to 'Hackathon'

9:30 – 11:30 'Hackathon' (break as needed)

11:30 – 12:00 Presentation & Discussion

12:00 – 13:00 Lunch break

13:00 – 13:50 Intro. to FAIRification plan

13:50 – 14:00 Break

14:00 – 14:50 Working session

14:50 – 15:00 Break

15:00 – 16:00 (17:00) Closing session

- Brief recap of the tools through the cycle
- Students share what data they brought and on which FAIRification stage and tool they will focus

- Students work on FAIRifying their own data sets

- Students briefly present their experiences FAIRifying their data

- Develop a 'FAIRification Roadmap' with the students for their data (connect with DMPs)

- Students work on their FAIRification Roadmap

- Final questions and discussion
- Summarize learnings

- Extra hour to offer further FAIRifying assistance

FAIRification Tools

FIP Wizard Data Stewardship Wizard	CEDAR templates Nanobench YODA	CEDAR templates Nanobench OpenRefine YODA	Nanobench FAIR Data Point YODA	Repositories: Dataverse, 4TU, DANS data stations, Zenodo	Repositories: Dataverse, 4TU, DANS data stations, Zenodo
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Actions according to FAIR Principles

Develop a FAIRification Roadmap for Research	<p>R1.2: Document what you do</p> <p>I1: Implement procedure for knowledge representation (data model)</p> <p>F2, I2, R1.3: Implement choice of metadata and data fields</p>	<p>R1.2: Document what you do</p> <p>I1: Follow procedure for knowledge representation (data model)</p> <p>F2, I2, R1.3: Follow choice of metadata and data fields</p>	<p>A1.1, A1.2: Define the protocols for access</p> <p>R1.1: Define a clear usage license (The above choices will impact the choice of repository)</p>	<p>F1, F3, F4, A1, A2, I3, R1: Deposit data with metadata and documentation for interoperability and reusability with repository</p>	<p>F1: Make sure you cite data with its persistent identifier</p>
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Completed

1. Gather and map FAIRification tools and methods over the RDM lifecycle

 Completed

2. Outline of course content, schedule, and time investment for participants

3. Explore level of maturity of tools and/or adapt them to one or more LEI/LUMC organization-specific approaches, including what would be needed to do that

4. Clarify (for each step) which tools or methods are best for implementation by LEI/LUMC today and supply them to LEI/LUMC researchers

5. Clarify (for each step) the role of the researcher vs. data steward

6. Research materials from other courses for input on organization

7. Define the different roles and experts needed to support course/workshop content and organization plus where/how to find these experts

8. Provide an estimate of the time investment needed for course/workshop trainers

9. Write a course/workshop text (and supporting materials) for researchers that clarifies the FAIRification process over the research life cycle

10. Define explicitly the outcome or outcomes of the course/workshop and its short- and long-term impact on research

Extra information

Universiteit
Leiden

1. FAIR Principles <https://www.gofair.foundation/interpretation>
2. FAIR Principles https://www.go-fair.org/wp-content/uploads/2022/01/FAIRPrinciples_overview.pdf
3. FAIR Principles <https://www.go-fair.org/fair-principles/>
4. FAIR Principles <https://www.nature.com/articles/sdata201618>
5. FIP Wizard <https://fip-wizard.ds-wizard.org>
6. FIP Wizard COVID-19 <https://fip-wizard.ds-wizard.org/projects/8c681c55-3dc8-42eb-93dd-8b27cf40bcc3>
7. Data Stewardship Wizard <https://ds-wizard.org>
8. CEDAR <https://metadatacenter.org>
9. RightField <https://rightfield.org.uk>
10. Ontop <https://ontop-vkg.org>
11. Nanobench <https://github.com/peta-pico/nanobench>
12. Nanopublications <https://nanopub.org/wordpress/>
13. OpenRefine <https://openrefine.org>
14. FAIR data point <https://www.fairdatapoint.org>
15. YODA <https://servicedesk.surf.nl/wiki/display/WIKI/Yoda+Hosting>
16. Zenodo <https://zenodo.org>
17. 4TU <https://www.4tu.nl>
18. DANS Data Station: Life, Health and Medical Sciences <https://dans.knaw.nl/en/data-stations/life-health-and-medical-sciences/>
19. Dataverse <https://dataverse.nl>

Findable

F1 (meta)data are assigned a globally unique and persistent identifier

F2 data are described with rich metadata

F3 metadata clearly and explicitly include the identifier of the data it describes

F4 (meta)data are registered or indexed in a searchable resource

Accessible

A1 (meta)data are retrievable by their identifier using a standardized communications protocol

A1.1 the protocol is open, free, and universally implementable

A1.2 the protocol allows for an authentication and authorization procedure, where necessary

A2 metadata are accessible, even when the data are no longer available

Interoperable

I1 (meta)data use a formal, accessible, shared, and broadly applicable language for knowledge representation

I2 (meta)data use vocabularies that follow FAIR principles

I3 (meta)data include qualified references to other (meta)data

Reusable

R1 (meta)data are richly described with a plurality of accurate and relevant attributes

R1.1 (meta)data are released with a clear and accessible data usage license

R1.2 (meta)data are associated with detailed provenance

R1.3 (meta)data meet domain-relevant community standards

Providing guidance for improving findability, accessibility, interoperability, and reusability of digital resources

